

Synthesis of Bis-(Glyoxalimine arylhydrazones)*

AJIT SINGH** & B. HIRSCH

Institute of Colour Chemistry, Technical University of Dresden

Received 28 November 1970

The Schiff bases from benzoyl acetone and polymethylene diamines, prepared by known methods have been coupled with diazonium salts to give bis-(glyoxalimine arylhydrazones).

In an earlier publication¹, a series of new bis(glyoxalimine arylhydrazones) of general structure I were reported. These compounds are prepared by coupling diazonium salts with alcoholic solutions of Schiff bases obtained by condensation of acetyl acetone (2 moles)

$R_1 = \text{H, alkyl, alkoxy, nitro group, halogen atom etc.}$

$R_2 = \text{CH}_3$

$n = 2, 3, 4, 5 \text{ or } 6.$

with polymethylene diamines (1 mole). Herein we report the preparation of compounds (II) wherein $R_2 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ in structure I. These compounds are also prepared from the Schiff bases²⁻⁴ (III) obtained from benzoyl acetone (2 moles) and polymethylene diamines (1 mole).

With regard to the above structure, it is noteworthy that the phenyl ring is attached to the carbon atom of the azomethine group and not to that of the keto group⁵.

These Schiff bases (III) are insoluble in water, but soluble in usual organic solvents. The corresponding acetyl-acetone derivatives are comparatively less stable than III⁶. This may be due to the higher resonance energy of phenyl nucleus (III) in place of methyl group present in the acetyl acetone derivatives.

In order to prepare II, 0.05 mole of the Schiff's base is dissolved in 200 ml pyridine. This solution is dropped into 100 ml water under efficient mechanical agitation so that a fine suspension is obtained. The suspension is cooled to 0° and coupled with a diazonium

* From D.Sc. Thesis submitted to the Technical University of Dresden by Ajit Singh.

** Present address : Chief Inspectorate of Textiles and clothing P. Box 294, Kanpur (U.P.)

salt prepared from 0.1 mole of an aromatic amine after neutralising with a saturated solution of sodium acetate. At the end of coupling, the reaction mass is diluted with 100 ml water to precipitate the dyestuff. It is filtered off, washed several times with water, dried and crystallised from suitable solvent or a mixture thereof. The compounds prepared by this method are listed in Table 1 (A & B).

The compounds are coloured and crystalline in appearance, possessing sharp melting points. They are soluble in benzene, pyridine, dimethyl formamide, acetone and chloroform but sparingly soluble in ethanol or methanol. They also yield tricyclic metal chelates with divalent metal ions such as Cu^{+2} , Ni^{+2} , Co^{+2} and bistriazolium salts by suitable oxidizing agent⁷.

TABLE 1(A)

(Bis-Glyoxalimine arylhydrazones) (II)

No.	R ₁	Crystallised form	Crystal shape	Yield %	m.p. °C
<i>n</i> = 2					
1.	H	CHCl ₃ : ethanol	Orange prisms	61.0	174-75
2.	CH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	„ „	Reddish brown prisms	55.0	213-15
3.	Cl(<i>p</i>)	„ „	Yellow prisms	67.5	202-04
4.	Br(<i>p</i>)	„ „	„	68.5	211-12
<i>n</i> = 3					
5.	H	— —	—	Could not be isolated	
6.	CH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	— —	—	-do-	
7.	OCH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	CHCl ₃ : methanol	Orange prisms	16.0	171-72
8.	Cl(<i>p</i>)	— —	—	Could not be isolated	
<i>n</i> = 4					
9.	H	Ethanol	Yellow needles	59.5	175-76
10.	CH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	CHCl ₃ : ethanol	Orange prisms	57.0	173-74
11.	OCH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	-do- -do-	Yellow needles	45.5	92-93
12.	Cl(<i>p</i>)	-do- -do-	Reddish brown prisms	33.5	174.5-75.5
<i>n</i> = 5					
13.	H	CHCl ₃ : ethanol	Yellow prisms	44.0	160-61
14.	OCH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	-do- -do-	Orange prisms	39.6	—
15.	OC ₂ H ₅ (<i>p</i>)	Ethanol	Yellow prisms	51.0	113-14
<i>n</i> = 6					
16.	H	CHCl ₃ : ethanol	Yellow prisms	26.0	168-70
17.	CH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	Dimethyl : ethanol formamide	Red prisms	55.0	161-63
18.	OCH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	CHCl ₃ : ethanol	Yellow prisms	53.5	161-62

TABLE 1(B)

Sl. No.	Molecular formula	Elemental Analysis						*Max.m μ	
		%N		%C		%H			
		Cal.	Found	Cal.	Found	Cal.	Found		
1.	C ₃₄ H ₃₂ N ₆ O ₂	15.10	15.13	73.36	73.43	5.80	6.44	230	371
2.	C ₃₆ H ₃₆ N ₆ O ₄	—	—	73.95	73.98	6.20	6.67	232	371
3.	C ₃₄ H ₃₀ N ₆ O ₂ Cl ₂	13.44	13.64	11.34	11.21 (Cl)	—	—	237	374
4.	C ₃₄ H ₃₀ N ₆ O ₂ Br ₂	11.75	11.75	—	—	—	—	238	376
5.	C ₃₅ H ₃₄ N ₆ O ₂	—	—	—	—	—	—	Not separable	
6.	C ₃₇ H ₃₈ N ₆ O ₂	—	—	—	—	—	—	Not separable	
7.	C ₃₇ H ₃₆ N ₆ O ₄	13.30	13.45	70.50	70.69	6.03	6.97	240	376
8.	C ₃₅ H ₃₂ N ₆ O ₂ Cl ₂	—	—	—	—	—	—	Not separable	
9.	C ₃₆ H ₃₆ N ₆ O ₂	14.37	14.02	73.94	74.11	6.21	7.15	236	370
10.	C ₃₈ H ₄₀ N ₆ O ₂	13.72	13.75	74.78	74.59	6.58	7.52	240	373
11.	C ₃₈ H ₄₀ N ₆ O ₄	13.03	13.08	70.75	70.44	6.26	6.97	238	373
12.	C ₃₆ H ₃₄ N ₆ O ₂ Cl ₂	12.88	12.62	—	—	—	—	240	374
13.	C ₃₇ H ₃₈ N ₆ O ₂	14.01	14.32	—	—	—	—	234	369
14.	C ₃₉ H ₄₂ N ₆ O ₄	12.78	12.90	—	—	—	—	239	375
15.	C ₄₁ H ₄₆ N ₆ O ₄	12.25	12.26	—	—	—	—	239	375
16.	C ₃₈ H ₄₀ N ₆ O ₂	—	—	74.48	74.46	6.58	7.19	237	368
17.	C ₄₀ H ₄₄ N ₆ O ₂	—	—	74.97	74.70	6.92	7.38	238	372
18.	C ₄₀ H ₄₄ N ₆ O ₄	12.40	12.39	71.50	71.55	6.60	7.53	239	375

* The UV-spectra of saturated solutions in ethanol were taken qualitatively by means of Gitter Spectrophotometer "CF₄ NJ optical milano".

One of the authors (A.S.) is thankful to the Govt. of the G.D.R. for grant of a scholarship and to Shri Ram Institute for Industrial Research, Delhi for grant of study leave.

REFERENCES

1. Ajit Singh and B. Hirsch, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 756.
2. P. J. McCarthy, R. J. Hovey, K. Ueno and A. E. Martell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 5820.
3. A. E. Martell, R. L. Belford and M. Calvin, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1958, **5**, 170.
4. B. Benary, *Ber. Dtsch. Chem. Ges.*, 1927, **60**, 1835.
5. P. J. McCarthy and A. E. Martell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 264.
6. R. J. Hovey, J. J. O'Connell and A. E. Martell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 3189.
7. Ajit Singh and B. Hirsch, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 514.

